

ISic1009

I.Sicily inscription 1009

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 122

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. μινῆσθητι ὁ θεὸς(εὐ) τῆς
2. δούλης σου Χρυσίδος
3. καὶ δὸς αὐτῇ χώραν φω
4. τινὴν τόπον ἀναψύ
5. ξεως εἰς κόλφους Ἄβρα
6. ἄμ Ἰσαὰκ κ(αὶ) Ἰακώβ ἀνηπαλύ
7. σατο ἢ μακαρίας μνήμης [τ]ῆ
8. πρὸ α νωνῶν Μαίων
9. [---]ΥΤΙΕΚΤΔ(vac.unknown)Ψ
10. [---]ΕΙΤΔ(vac.unknown)Δ

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes based on Kaibel's diplomatic transcription

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492636

EDCS 39102163

PHI 140487

PHI 331428

Bibliography

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